

USING TYPES OF TRANSLATION WITH THE INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES DURING THE LESSONS

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Annotation

The article deals the benefit of using the types of translation with innovative technologies in teaching foreign languages.

Key words

desirable qualification, bilingual identity, advocate translation, method, complementarity, project-based learning, team spirit, verbal competence, communicative approach, project method.

ДАРСЛАР ДАВОМИДА ИННОВАЦИОН ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР ОРҚАЛИ ТАРЖИМА ТУРЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ

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Аннотация: *Мақолада чет тилларини ўқитишда инновацион технологиялар билан таржима турларидан фойдаланишнинг афзаллиги кўриб чиқилган.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ВИДОВ ПЕРЕВОДА С ПОМОЩЬЮ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ВО ВРЕМЯ УРОКОВ

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Аннотация: *В статье рассматривается преимущество использования видов перевода с инновационными технологиями в преподавании иностранных языков.*

Many job notices for positions in English language teaching and applied linguistics specify knowledge of technology as an essential or desirable qualification. Warschauer (2000) predicts even more sweeping changes in job requirements for teachers in the future, whereas Cribb (2000) speculates a diminished need for English teachers in a world where language users can employ convenient translation technologies rather than engaging in time-intensive language study! Critical perspectives warn applied linguists not to accept the technologizing of the profession as inevitable.

Many people also find the tackling of translation problems intellectually stimulating and aesthetically satisfying. In addition, it helps create and maintain good relations between teacher and student, facilitates classroom management and control, and allows students to maintain their own sense of first language identity, while also building a new bilingual identity. It does not seem to impede efficient language use – many students who began their studies through translation go on to become fluent and accurate users of the new language.

A main factor that has some practitioners advocate translation is that it lends itself to “easy” teaching. How simple is it to get students to translate or to explain in the first language. Think for a moment, when we learnt our first language, we mastered it without the need for translation. Those capacities we had then, we still have now, and I would suggest even more. So why not use them and have learners come to understandings of the new language by using their awareness, wits, their intelligence, their perception. All of this usage making them better language learners. The trick for the language teacher is to teach in ways that encourage these practices but to not to replace translation with copious explanations and practices that dull the mind, or at the very least don’t stimulate it to grow.

Today, the goals and tasks facing the modern education are changing – the emphasis is shifted from the assimilation of knowledge to the formation of competence. There is a reorientation of a personal-oriented approach, the opposite of knowledge-oriented impersonal pedagogy. Schools are provided with modern computers, electronic resources, Internet access. This contributes to the introduction of new pedagogical technologies in the teaching and educational process. It is the use of innovative technologies in English language lessons is the main sign of positive results of creative activity, which entails increased motivation of students.

According to scientific calculations of national and foreign scientists, the term “method” has two basic meanings:

- A certain path to the goal, means to achieve the result.

- Complete methodological system and the fundamental direction of the learning process, which prevail in the various periods of the science development

With the development of high-tech usual methods of teaching through books, similar grammar exercises, reading and translation of texts go on the back burner.[2] The humanistic approach eventually led to the formation of the communicative approach, on which is based the whole procedure. Traditional grammar-translation methods do not form language skills. The student is capable to read and translate various texts at high-level, but he is not able to apply the knowledge of a foreign language in real life situations. The communicative approach allows the use of grammatical knowledge in a form of speaking and writing skills. One of the key tasks is the enriching of vocabulary. However, new words must be stored not only in a passive, but also in active form. In other words, the student must not only know the translation of a word, but should be able to use it in speech or in writing of own texts. As a simple exercise to develop skills can be noted spontaneous group dialogues. Students are divided into pairs and try to communicate on various topics. Usually the teacher oversees the conversation or helping with leading questions. During learning of new words used exercises with cards. On them written new words, and then they are turned and mixed. One student draws a card and tries to explain the meaning of a foreign word so the others can guess it. This exercise allows you to “feel” new words and remember situations in which they are used correctly. At a certain stage of development can be implemented into the learning process different movies in a foreign language. Students are asked questions, the answers to which should be identified directly from watched videos.

In recent years, increasingly it raises the question of the application of innovative technology in the classroom. It is not only new facilities but also new forms and methods of teaching, new approach to learning. Introduction of innovative technologies in the educational process is interconnected with the improvement of the content and methods of education in the process of teaching foreign languages in relation to the needs of modern life.

The main objective of foreign language teaching is the formation and development of the communicative culture of pupils, learning practical mastery of a foreign language. The task of the teacher is to create the conditions of practical language learning for each student to choose such training methods that would allow each student to show their activity, their creativity. Modern teaching techniques such as cooperative learning, project methodology, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources help to realize the learner centered

approach to learning, providing personalization and differentiation of learning abilities of children, taking into account their level of training.[3] The communicative approach is a strategy that simulates the communication, aimed at creating a psychological and linguistic readiness to communicate, on a conscious understanding of the material and methods of action with him. For the user, the implementation of the communicative approach in the Internet is not particularly difficult. Communicative job must offer students a problem or question for discussion, and students do not just share information, but also evaluate it. But the main criterion to distinguish this approach from other types of learning activities is that students choose their own linguistic units to process their thoughts. Using the Internet in the communicative approach could not be better motivated: its aim is to interest students in learning a foreign language through the accumulation and expansion of their knowledge and experience. One of the basic requirements for teaching foreign languages using the Internet resources, is to create interaction in the classroom, what is called in interactive methods. Interactivity is a «unification, coordination and complementarity of efforts communicative purpose and outcome of speech means». Teaching genuine language, the Internet helps in shaping the conversation, as well as in teaching vocabulary and grammar, providing a genuine interest and, hence, efficiency. Interactivity is not just creating real situations of life, but also makes the students to adequately respond to them through a foreign language

Project method is one of the most pressing contemporary technologies in teaching foreign languages. It combines the elements of problem-based learning and collaborative learning that allows achieving the highest level of mastery of any subject, and foreign language in particular. Project method forms students' communication skills, culture, communication, the ability concisely and audibly formulate thoughts, be tolerant to the opinion of partners in communication and develops the ability to extract information from a variety of sources, to process it with the help of modern technologies. All these factors create language environment that - results in the appearance of the natural need to interact in a foreign language.

Project-based learning does not contradict the traditional ways of learning. It helps to activate students since most of them have an interest for new knowledge. Such kind of motivation - the desire to successfully develop theme of the project - is often stronger than the demands of parents and teachers to study hard in order to get excellent and good marks.

The main purpose of the use of this innovative approach is the ability to effectively master students' foreign communicative competence. It includes the following concepts:

- verbal competence is creating an opportunity of manifestation of communicative skills in all forms: listening, speaking, writing, reading, translation within a specific topic;
- socio-cultural competence is the formation of ideas about the social and cultural specificity of the target language;
- linguistic competence is students' acquisition of lexical units relating to the topic as a necessary basis for registration of speaking abilities;
- educational and cognitive competence is the improvement of educational activity on mastering of foreign languages;
- compensatory competence is formation of skills of overcoming difficult situations in a shortage of linguistic resources.

Also, this approach forms informational competence which manifests the ability to work independently with reference books, find necessary information in various sources, and see links with other branches of knowledge.[4] Moreover, project-based learning contributes to enhancing students' personal confidence, developing a "team spirit" and communication skills; providing a mechanism for critical thinking, the ability to find ways to solve problems and developing students' research skills.

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